

BUCKLING OF AN ELLIPTIC SUBLAMINATE

Huyan Xiaozhi and Liu Fanglong
Beijing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics

The buckling of a elliptic sublaminde located near one surface of laminate was studied in this paper. As shown in Figure 1, the set of intact laminate delamination from a laminate is referred to as the "sublaminde" and the remaining laminate as "base laminate". A strain ϵ is loaded to the laminate in the X-direction. The associated strains in the Y-direction and shear strain are $-\nu_{12}\epsilon$ and $\nu_{16}\epsilon$ respectively. Suppose h to be small compared to the base laminate thickness and Semiaxes a and b . Hence, thin plate linear buckling theory is valid to sublaminde and the inplane strains around the sublaminde boundary can be calculated from the laminate inplane deformation.

Firstly, the Strains of laminate in the xyz coordinate is obtained by using the translation of strains^[4]

$$\{\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y, \nu_{xy}\}^T = [1 - \nu_{12} \quad \nu_{16}]^T T^T \epsilon \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. Model for a buckled Sublaminde

Here, T is the translation Matrix. Then, the inplane forces are

$$[N_x \quad N_y \quad N_{xy}]^T = \{\epsilon_x \quad \epsilon_y \quad \nu_{xy}\}^T [A] = [n_x \quad n_y \quad n_{xy}]^T [A] \epsilon \quad (2)$$

in which, A is inplane stiffness matrix of sublaminde and

$$[n_x \quad n_y \quad n_{xy}]^T = [1 - \nu_{12} \quad \nu_{16}]^T T^T [A] \quad (3)$$

The buckling shape of the sublaminar is shown in Figure 1 (b) and the deflection w is measured from the sublaminar mid-plane, Along the Sublaminar boundary, the transverse displacements and slopes are zero. Now, the buckling initiation problem is reduced to that of an idealized elliptic sublaminar subjected to a set of inplane forces as shown in Figure 1 (c).

Assume the deflection of sublaminar in the z -direction as a function of the coordinates x and y

$$w = [1 - (\frac{x}{a})^2 - (\frac{y}{b})^2] \{C_0 + C_1x^2 + C_2y^2 + C_3xy\} \quad (4)$$

The principal of minimum potential energy

$$\delta \pi = \delta (U - W) = 0 \quad (5)$$

is applied to obtain a system of simultaneous equations for the constants

$$\{C\}^T = \{C_0 \ C_1 \ C_2 \ C_3\}$$

$$\{[K] - \epsilon [K_g]\} \{C\} = 0 \quad (6)$$

Here, U is strain energy of sublaminar and W is the work done by the midplane stresses. The stiffness matrix K is

$$[K] = D_{11}[K_1] + D_{22}[K_2] + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})[K_3] + 2D_{16}[K_4] + 2D_{26}[K_5] \quad (7)$$

and K_g , is the geometrix stiffness matrix

$$[K_g] = n_x [K_{g1}] + n_y [K_{g2}] + n_{xy} [K_{g3}] \quad (8)$$

Compared with reference [1], a term C_3xy is added in deflection w which reflects the bending-torsion effect of the sublaminar during bending. There are matrices K_{16} and K_{26} in stiffness matrix (7) corresponding the constants D_{16} and D_{26} respectively. There is matrix K_{g12} in geometric stiffness matrix (8) which corresponds N_{xy} . The contribution of the shear-extension coupling constants A_{16} and A_{26} to work W are made to reflect. Therefore, the method used in this paper is better than that in reference [1] and can be used for any symmetric sublaminar.

Buckling Strain of a surface sublaminar in a composite laminate is dependent on the sublaminar thickness h , the Semiaxes a and b , the base laminate Poisson's ratios ν_{12} and ν_{16} , the sublaminar angle θ , and fiber angle of each lamina α . That $E_1 = 131.0\text{GPa}$, $E_t = 13.0\text{GPa}$, $G = 6.4\text{GPa}$, $\nu_{et} = 0.34$, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{16} = 0$, $h = 0.51\text{mm}$ was taken as same as that in reference [1], From the result of calculation, it is concluded that:

1. The method used in this paper fits to calculate the critical strains of all symmetric elliptic sublaminars delaminate from a base laminate.
2. The buckling strains of unidirectional sublaminars reduce when the parameter $\lambda = b/a$ increase.
3. The critical strains of unidirectional sublaminars raise when the fiber angle α increases. The change is complex and affected by the parameter λ .
4. The change of the buckling strains with the parameter λ is not affected by the base laminate Poisson's ratio ν_{16} . The critical strains raise as the base laminate Poisson's ratio ν increases and the slopes of their increasing raise for increasing

the fiber angle α of unidirectional sublaminate.

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